

DEVELOPMENT OF SUSTAINABLE MANUFACTURING PROTOCOL OF 'GOLDEN TIPS TEA' WITH DIFFERENT CLONAL COMBINATIONS IN RESPECT OF BANGLADESH

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Abstract

The cheapest beverage after water is tea which is also becoming more and more well-known as a significant "health drink" due to its possible therapeutic benefits. The present experiment was carried out to develop a standardized manufacturing protocol for 'Golden Tips Tea' by using different clonal combinations in respect of Bangladesh. The whole experiment was conducted in the following two steps. In first step, five treatments with four replications based on oxidation time ($T_1 = 60$ minutes, $T_2 = 70$ minutes, $T_3 = 80$ minutes, $T_4 = 90$ minutes, and $T_5 = 100$ minutes) were used to standardize the protocol. After standardizing the manufacturing protocol, second step was conducted to develop quality-full Golden Tips Tea by using buds of three different clonal varieties with their nine combinations ($C_1 = 100\%$ BT2, $C_2 = 50\%$ BT2 + 50% BT4, $C_3 = 80\%$ BT2 + 20% BT4, $C_4 = 100\%$ BT4, $C_5 = 50\%$ BT4 + 50% BT23, $C_6 = 80\%$ BT4 + 20% BT23, $C_7 = 100\%$ BT23, $C_8 = 50\%$ BT2 + 50% BT23, $C_9 = 80\%$ BT2 + 20% BT23) in respect of Bangladesh. The manufacturing protocol of T_4 treatment (65% withering + ideal rolling + oxidation for 90 minutes + drying at 180-200°F for 30 minutes) with the varietal combination of 80% BT2 + 20% BT4 (C_3) gave the best result for producing Golden Tips Tea. Better quality Golden Tips Tea can also be produced by the combination of C_1 (100% BT2) and C_9 (80% BT2 + 20% BT23). But, in the case of producing bulk amount of Golden Tips Tea, using only BT23 (C_7 combination) could be more cost-effective which was 'Above Average' quality type. During whole experiment, room temperature was maintained 86 °F (30 °C) and relative humidity at 94% was strictly followed.

Keywords: Golden Tips Tea, Quality, Manufacturing Protocol, Clonal Combination

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Introduction

Since ancient times, drinking tea has been associated with health benefits (Khan and Mukhtar, 2013). With its possible therapeutic potential, it has been increasingly gaining acceptance as a significant "health drink" (Hicks, 2009). Due to its abundance of healthy amino acids, vitamins and antioxidants, tea's prominence has gradually increased over the past few decades (Lin et al., 2019). Tea has a variety of secondary metabolites that are directly linked to its quality, including free amino acids, polyphenols and alkaloids, which are all extremely aromatic, flavorful and beneficial to health (Too et al., 2015).

Due to specific requirements of climate and soil, tea cultivation is confined only to certain specific regions of the world. Since 1854, when the first tea garden 'Malnicherra Tea Estate' in Sylhet was established, tea has been grown commercially in Bangladesh (Arefin and Hossain, 2022). Being one of the main agro-based sectors, tea is a significant cash crop in Bangladesh. In 2023, about 168 tea estates produced 102.92 million kg of made tea. (BTB, 2023).

The increasing demand for tea along with this rapidly growing population of Bangladesh has created a huge domestic market for the tea industry in Bangladesh. In addition to increasing the production of tea, there is a need to improve the quality of tea and add diversification. Although tea production in recent years was as expected, tea auction prices were not so much satisfactory level. To survive in the export market, besides reducing the cost of production, the production quality of tea should be increased as well and tea diversification should be introduced.

Different types of teas are manufactured in other countries based on people's tastes, habits, and culture. Tea may generally be divided into three categories according to how it is processed: fully oxidized tea- (i) CTC black tea, (ii) Orthodox black tea, (iii) Golden Tips Tea, partially oxidized tea (i) Oolong tea (ii) Yellow tea and fully non-oxidized tea (i) Green tea, (ii) White tea (Arefin et al, 2020). 'Golden Tips Tea' is a kind of oxidized tea that differs from its golden colour appearance and excellent flavour i.e., Taste & Aroma. Since "Golden Tips Tea" requires an extensive amount of labor and years of actual skill, it might be considered an instance of "Artisan Tea" The Golden Tips Tea is created from the young buds of select tea bushes, and cultivating them requires a keen understanding of both the tea plant and the environment in which they grow. The plucking process is an art in itself, where only the very best leaves are handpicked to ensure the highest quality. The buds are subject to prolonged oxidation, allowing them to retain their golden colour and exquisite taste.

In Bangladesh, there is not enough literature or production manufacturing knowledge about Golden Tips Tea thus planters are still more or less ignorant about Golden Tips Tea processing. This paper will give a concrete idea about the standardized manufacturing protocol of Golden Tips Tea using different clonal combinations of Bangladesh.

Material and methods

Two experiments were carried out subsequently at BTRI Miniature Factory from March 2023 to December 2023 to develop a sustainable manufacturing protocol for Golden Tips Tea in Bangladesh. The whole experiment was conducted in the following two steps.

1. Standardizing the protocol: The manufacturing protocol of the Golden Tips Tea was standardized in this step. Based on oxidation time five treatments with four replications were used in this step. Fresh buds of the BT2 cultivar were initially harvested, and rigorous adherence to 65% withering and optimum rolling was maintained throughout the production process. After oxidation of different treatments, immediately drying at 180-200 °F for 30 minutes was repeated to bring down the moisture to 3%. During this experiment, room temperature was maintained 86 °F (30 °C) and relative humidity at 94% was strictly followed. To obtain good quality golden tips tea, the only unopened bud was plucked and processed. Unopened hairy buds are commonly desired for the best quality of golden tips tea. Treatments of this step are given below:

Treatments	Manufacturing protocol
T ₁	= Withering + Rolling + Oxidation for 60 minutes + Drying
T ₂	= Withering + Rolling + Oxidation for 70 minutes + Drying
T ₃	= Withering + Rolling + Oxidation for 80 minutes + Drying
T ₄	= Withering + Rolling + Oxidation for 90 minutes + Drying
T ₅	= Withering + Rolling + Oxidation for 100 minutes + Drying

2. Effect of different clonal combination: After standardizing the manufacturing protocol, this step was conducted to develop quality-full Golden Tips Tea by using different clones with their different combinations in respect of Bangladesh. Three BTRI-released clonal varieties, such as BT2, BT4 and BT23 along with nine combinations having each of four replications were used in this step, as follows:

Treatments	Manufacturing protocol
C ₁	= Golden Tips Tea from only BT2.
C ₂	= Golden Tips Tea from 50% BT2 + 50% BT4.
C ₃	= Golden Tips Tea from 80% BT2 + 20% BT4.
C ₄	= Golden Tips Tea from only BT4.
C ₅	= Golden Tips Tea from 50% BT4 + 50% BT23.
C ₆	= Golden Tips Tea from 80% BT4 + 20% BT23.
C ₇	= Golden Tips Tea from only BT23.
C ₈	= Golden Tips Tea from 50% BT2 + 50% BT23
C ₉	= Golden Tips Tea from 80% BT2 + 20% BT23

Here, the variety BT2 has a consistent touch of flavour as like as Orchids while BT4 is a quality clone (having the characteristics of malty taste) and BT23 has silver needle long tips (Hossain et al, 2018; BTRI, 2021).

Traditional organoleptic tea tasting method was used to evaluate the quality of each Golden Tips Tea treatments. During quality test, dry leaf appearance, infused leaf appearance and liquor characteristics were assessed and scored numerically out of 50 marks, as mentioned below:

Table 1. Parameters of conventional organoleptic tasting of Golden Tips Tea

Parameters	Points
1. Dry Leaf Appearance	10 points
2. Infused Leaf Appearance	10 points
3. Liquor characteristics (30 points):	
3.1. Liquor colour	10 points
3.2. Flavour	10 points
3.3. Brightness	10 points
Total =	50 points

Quality scores were recorded and analyzed statistically using 'Statistix 10' for every parameter. For categorize Golden Tips Tea, we developed a "Quality Category" based on organoleptic tasting scoring (out of 50 points) which is as below:

Table 2. Quality category of golden tips tea

Quality category	Score
E = Excellent	≥ 34 out of 50
AA = Above Average	34 > to ≥ 32 out of 50
A = Average	32 > to ≥ 30 out of 50
BA = Below Average	<32 out of 50

Results and Discussion

1. Standardizing the protocol

Based on five oxidation times (60, 70, 80, 90 and 100 minutes), the manufacturing protocol of the Golden Tips Tea was standardized. The main characteristics of Golden Tips Tea are 'Golden Tippy' like dry leaf appearance, infused leaf of 'Coppery bright' color with high flavour and 'Golden Bright' brightness.

From Table 3, it was found that, a 'Golden Tippy' like dry leaf appearance was found in T₄ treatment (7.51) which was followed by T₂ treatment (6.93) and T₃ treatment (6.89). The inferior quality was observed in T₅ treatment (6.79) which was 'Dark Tippy' as well as T₁ treatment (6.81) due to prolonged oxidation. In the case of infused leaf appearance, 'Coppery bright' color infused leaf was observed in T₄ treatment (6.42) which was followed by both T₃ treatment (6.24) and T₅ treatment (6.23) were statistically similar. 'Very good color' liquor was found in T₄ treatment (7.45) which was followed by both T₁ treatment (7.19) and T₅ treatment (7.21) were statistically similar. Interestingly, in case of flavour, 'High' flavour (6.15) was observed both T₄ and T₅ treatment while 'Medium' flavour was found in rest of the treatments. Again, Brightness of 'Golden Bright' color was found in T₄ treatment (7.41) while inferior brightness was observed in both T₁ treatment (7.14) and T₅ treatment (7.15) were statistically similar.

Based on the total points and quality category from Table 3, it was revealed that the 'Excellent' quality (34.94) type Golden Tips Tea was obtained by maintaining the manufacturing protocol of T₄ treatment (65% withering + ideal rolling + oxidation for 90 minutes + drying at 180-200 °F for 30 minutes) followed by T₃ treatment (33.67), T₅ treatment (33.53), T₂ treatment (33.52) and T₁ treatment (32.97) gave 'Above Average' Quality Category.

So, from this experiment it can be concluded that, superior quality Golden Tips Tea can be obtained by 65% withering + ideal rolling + oxidation for 90 minutes + drying at 180-200 °F for 30 minutes where room temperature at 86 °F (30 °C) and relative humidity at 94% will be strictly maintained.

Table 3. Liquor characteristics with scoring of Golden Tips Tea of different treatments.

Treatments	Dry Leaf Appearance (10 Points)	Infused Leaf Appearance (10 Points)	Liquor Colour (10 Points)	Flavour (10 Points)	Brightness (10 Points)	Total Points (50)	Quality Category**
T ₁ (60 min)	6.81 d (Tippy)	5.74 c (Fairly Bright)	7.19 b (fair color)	6.09 ab (Medium)	7.14 b (Bright)	32.97	AA
T ₂ (70 min)	6.93 ab (Silvery Tippy)	5.98 bc (Quite Bright)	7.29 ab (good color)	6.11 ab (Medium)	7.21 ab (Fairly Bright)	33.52	AA
T ₃ (80 min)	6.89 bc (Tippy)	6.24 b (Bright)	7.31 ab (good color)	6.04 b (Medium)	7.19 ab (Fairly Bright)	33.67	AA
T ₄ (90 min)	7.51 a (Golden Tippy)	6.42 a (Coppery bright)	7.45 a (Very good color)	6.15 a (High)	7.41 a (Golden Bright)	34.94	E
T ₅ (100 min)	6.79 d (Dark Tippy)	6.23 b (Bright)	7.21 b (fair color)	6.15 a (High)	7.15 b (Bright)	33.53	AA
LSD at 5% level of Significance*	0.04	0.17	0.12	0.05	0.08	-	-

* Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

** E = Excellent, AA = Above Average, A = Average and BA = Below Average

2. Effect of different clonal combination

Three BTRI-released clonal varieties, such as BT2, BT4, and BT23 along with their nine combinations were used in this step to study the different clonal effects on produced golden tips tea. Some parameters of fresh bud of different clonal varieties were studied which was provide in Table 4. It was observed that long fresh bud (4.61 cm) and higher 1000 fresh bud weight (65.27 g) was found in BT23 while smaller bud size (2.93 cm) and lower 1000 fresh bud weight (51.75 g) were found in BT4 clonal variety. The number of pubescence was observed more in BT4 (1825) while lower in BT23 (1628).

Table 4. Some parameters of fresh bud of different clonal varieties

Clonal varieties	Fresh Bud size (cm)	1000 Fresh Bud Weight (g)	Number of Pubescence
BT2	3.56 b	56.68 b	1684 b
BT4	2.93 c	51.75 c	1825 a
BT23	4.61 a	65.27 a	1628 c
LSD at 5% level of Significance*	0.59	4.84	54.47

* Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

Fresh buds of nine combinations of three clonal varieties were collected and Golden Tips Tea was produced through standardized protocol (65% withering + ideal rolling + oxidation for 90 minutes + drying at 180-200°F for 30 minutes) stated above. From Table 5, it was observed that, dry leaf appearances of all combinations were 'Golden Tippy' type, but best 'Golden Tippy' appearance was observed in C₁ combination (7.45). There was no significant deference in infused leaf appearance because standardized protocol was followed. 'Very good liquor color' was found in C₃ combination (7.47) with C₁ combination (7.43). 'High' flavour due to 80% BT2 flavour as like as Orchids and 20% BT4 (deserves the characteristics of Malty tastes with golden bright liquor colour) was noticed in C₁ combination (6.17). C₃ combination (6.17) with C₉ combination (6.08) also gave high flavour. 'Golden Bright' type brightness was observed in both C₁ combination (7.42) and C₃ combination (7.41) while rest of the combinations were 'Fairly Bright'.

So, it was revealed that, clonal combination of C₃ (80% BT2 + 20% BT4), C₁ (only BT2) and C₉ (80% BT2 + 20% BT23) produced 'Excellent' quality golden tips tea. The highest quality score was performed by C₃ (34.91) along with C₁ (34.88) and C₉ (34.36) which were statistically similar. Plucking of leaf buds is very laborious and smaller-sized buds require more labour thus more expensive than prolonged-sized buds. The bud size and 1000 fresh bud weight of clonal variety BT23 are much more than the other clonal varieties, thus plucking of buds only from BT23 would be more cost-effective than the other combinations due to less plucking cost of labour. So, if any planter wants to produce bulk amount of golden tips tea, he can produce golden tips tea from only BT23 (C₇ combination) which could be 'Above Average' quality type (33.85).

Table 5. Liquor characteristics with scoring of Golden Tips Tea of different treatments.

Clonal combination	Dry Leaf Appearance (10 Points)	Infused Leaf Appearance (10 Points)	Liquor Colour (10 Points)	Flavour (10 Points)	Brightness (10 Points)	Total Points 50	Quality Category**
C ₁ (100% BT2)	7.45 a	6.41 (Coppery bright)	7.43 ab (Very good color)	6.17 a (High)	7.42 a (Golden Bright)	34.88	E
C ₂ (50% BT2 + 50% BT4)	7.22 cd	6.37 (Coppery bright)	7.32 cd (good color)	5.83 ab (Medium)	7.23 bc (Fairly Bright)	33.97	AA
C ₃ (80% BT2 + 20% BT4)	7.42 ab	6.44 (Coppery bright)	7.47 a (Very good color)	6.19 a (High)	7.41 ab (Golden Bright)	34.93	E
C ₄ (100% BT4)	7.37 bc	6.29 (Coppery bright)	7.33 cd (good color)	5.59 de (Medium)	7.25 bc (Fairly Bright)	33.93	AA
C ₅ (50% BT4 + 50% BT23)	7.21 d (Golden Tippy)	6.39 (Coppery bright)	7.34 bc (good color)	5.61 cd (Medium)	7.24 bc (Fairly Bright)	33.79	AA
C ₆ (80% BT4 + 20% BT23)	7.23 cd (Golden Tippy)	6.41 (Coppery bright)	7.35 bc (good color)	5.63 cd (Medium)	7.21 c (Fairly Bright)	33.83	AA
C ₇ (100% BT23)	7.36 bc (Golden Tippy)	6.38 (Coppery bright)	7.31 d (good color)	5.55 e (Medium)	7.25 bc (Fairly Bright)	33.85	AA
C ₈ (50% BT2 + 50% BT23)	7.22 cd (Golden Tippy)	6.32 (Coppery bright)	7.32 cd (good color)	5.83 bc (Medium)	7.24 bc (Fairly Bright)	33.93	AA
C ₉ (80% BT2 + 20% BT23)	7.24 cd (Golden Tippy)	6.43 (Coppery bright)	7.35 bc (good color)	6.08 ab (High)	7.26 bc (Fairly Bright)	34.36	E
LSD at 5% level of Significance*	0.05	ns	0.02	0.09	0.03	-	-

* Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

** E = Excellent, AA = Above Average, A = Average and BA = Below Average

Fig. 1. Silver needle buds of different clonal varieties

Fig. 2. Dry Leaf of 'Golden Tips Tea'

Fig. 3. Infusion of 'Golden Tips Tea'

Conclusion

The Golden Tips Tea is a very royal-class quality tea that looks just as premium as it tastes. Tea planters in Bangladesh can increase their profit margin by producing this tea. For producing Golden Tips Tea, the manufacturing protocol of T_4 treatment (65% withering + ideal rolling + oxidation for 90 minutes + drying at 180-200°F for 30 minutes) with the varietal combination of 80% BT2 + 20% BT4 (C_3) would be the best. Better quality Golden Tips Tea can also be produced by the combination of C_1 (100% BT2) and C_9 (80% BT2 + 20% BT23). But, in the case of producing a bulk amount of Golden Tips Tea, using only BT23 (C_7 combination) could be more cost-effective reducing plucking cost which was 'Above Average' quality type.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to acknowledge to Dr. AKM Rafikul Hoque (Director, Project Development Unit) for their helpful directions, suggestions and comments about scoring & making quality category of Golden Tips Tea.

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